

Machine Learning for Forecasting

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Introduction

My background

- 2008 Graduated in Computer Science, University of Ulm, Germany
- 2008-2013 Ph.D. in Computer Science and IT, University of Granada, Spain
 - Topic: Time Series Forecasting
 - Forecast Evaluation
 - Cross-validation for forecasting
 - Research stay at Dept of EBS, Monash University, Australia, with RJ Hyndman
 - Forecasting for fault detection in wind turbines
 - Forecasting for pest outbreaks in green houses
 - Predictive maintenance

My background (2)

- 2013-2014 Postdoc, Univ. Granada: Predictive Maintenance for railways
- 2014-2022 Research Fellow, Lecturer, Senior Lecturer at Dept of DSAI, Monash University
 - 3-year “Discovery Early Career Researcher Award” Fellowship to focus on time series forecasting
 - Renewable energy production forecasting (wind/solar)
 - Energy demand forecasting
 - Energy price forecasting
 - Retail sales/demand forecasting

My background (3)

- 10/2022-4/2023 Visiting Research Data Scientist at Meta Platforms Inc., Menlo Park, CA
 - capacity planning for server and network infrastructure for Facebook, Whatsapp, Instagram, Messenger
- Since 5/2023 María Zambrano (Senior) Fellow at DaSCI, UGR
 - Predict+Optimize: If a forecast feeds into an optimization, how can we make the two interact optimally?
 - E.g., for battery scheduling, supply chain, and others
- Currently: On a research stay at Monash

What I forecast

- Sales/demand forecasting in the supply chain, retail
- Forecasting in Energy
 - Demand
 - Prices
 - Renewable energy production
 - building efficiency
- Predictive maintenance (road, railway, ...mining)
- ...

What people think I forecast (but I don't)

- The weather
 - Lots of domain knowledge and specialised models exist
 - We leave it to the meteorologists
 - We often use weather forecasts as inputs to our models
- The stock market

Stock market forecasting (1)

Pros:

- Lots of freely available high-frequency data
- Clear motivation and use case (making money)

Stock market forecasting (2)

Cons:

- Shareprice not a function of its own past, but of its anticipated future
- Low signal to noise ratio
- Markets tend to be close to “efficient”
- Forecasting in efficient markets is not possible (beyond the naive forecast, i.e., using the last observation as the forecast)

→ Predicting stock market returns from just a couple of lags won't work, no matter what method you are using.

→ All this is true in a similar way for exchange rates!

**Where is the field of forecasting
right now?**

M competitions

- Forecasting competitions were a thing way before Kaggle
- Spyros Makridakis hosted the “M’ ’-competition in 1982
- 1998: M3 competition
- participants had to forecast 3003 time series
- categories: yearly, quarterly, monthly, other
- Had as a central conclusion that complex methods do not necessarily outperform simple methods
- Simple models were models like a random walk with drift: you take the last observation and add a constant to it
- The only neural network that participated was quite bad
- Won by the “theta” method, which is an average of a linear regression and SES with drift
- **The** benchmark dataset in forecasting for almost 20 years

Simple exponential smoothing (SES)

Forecasts from Simple exponential smoothing

red line: exponentially decaying weights, $\alpha = 0.62$.

Controversy of ML vs Statistical methods

Long-standing controversy in the forecasting field, whether Machine Learning or Statistical methods work better for forecasting

- Forecasters “knew” that simple methods work best
 - ... because they had won the M3, the NN3, the NN5
- Machine Learners “knew” that Neural Networks work best
 - ... because, hey, it's a NN, it's a universal approximator
- Thousands of papers in Neural Network journals and others
- “A Novel method X for stock market forecasting...”
- Cherry-picked datasets, no proper benchmarking

→ Every time I hear somebody say “XYZformer is the state-of-the-art in forecasting” I get reminded that this is still very relevant today.

Controversy of ML vs Statistical methods (cont'd)

S Makridakis, E Spiliotis, V Assimakopoulos (2018), Statistical and Machine Learning forecasting methods: Concerns and ways forward. PloS one 13 (3), e0194889.

- Makridakis et al. (2018b) benchmarked ML methods against statistical benchmarks
- not surprisingly, the ML methods lost
- The paper is published in PLOS ONE because it got rejected at 2-3 Neural Network outlets beforehand.

Controversy of ML vs Statistical methods (cont'd)

- Reasons for rejection were that: there are many ML methods that have “proven to overcome the results provided,” though the editors and reviewers didn't name any in particular
- Makridakis was upset over this and did what he seemingly does best when he is upset...organise another competition: the M4
- so that Machine Learners could submit forecasts and show that their methods work well

Controversy of ML vs Statistical methods (cont'd)

- The history explains why the forecasting field got so hung up on this controversy
- Still somewhat surprising as Forecasting emerged from Statistics just in the same way Machine Learning emerged from Statistics

-> Focus on OOS accuracy, not model properties

-> Some things were discovered in parallel in both fields:

- forecast combination (Bates and Granger, 1969) vs ensembling (in ML in the 1990s)
- simple methods vs regularisation

Controversy of ML vs Statistical methods (cont'd)

- Forecasters have been used to ML promising much and hardly delivering anything
- This has changed in recent years

M4 competition (2018)

- 100k series, across many different domains
- hourly, daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly, yearly series
- prediction intervals

Results

- published in Makridakis et al. (2018a)
- most forecasters expected that a combination approach of statistical methods would win
- however, such methods got 2nd and 3rd
- winner was ES-RNN, a hybrid between RNN and ETS, by Smyl (2020)
- a big surprise to many people that an ML model could win

How can ML work for forecasting?

Global models

- Traditionally, *one* time series is seen as a dataset
- One model is built per time series
- low sampling frequencies and non-stationarities like structural breaks make usually that we don't have enough data to fit complex (ML) models
- M3, M4 datasets are put together under this paradigm; very different series from different frequencies, different domains, etc.

Global models (cont'd)

Paradigm shift:

- a *set* of time series is a dataset (e.g., a set of series from retail, smart meters, etc.)
- build a model across the series
- names: global modelling, cross-learning, multi-task learning, pooled regression

-> Now, enough data, due to more series.

-> ML methods are competitive now

Global models (cont'd)

- Local model: typically fitting a model with few (<10) parameters to a single series
- if you have 10k series and fit 5 parameters, you end up with 50k parameters

-> fit a global model with 5k parameters instead

-> Overall complexity of set of local models grows when dataset grows; complexity of global model stays the same

Global models (cont'd)

- Global models can afford to be more complex
- Complexity can be added as:
 - longer memory (longer input windows, more lags)
 - non-linear/non-parametric models (NNs, GBT, ...)
 - data partitioning

M5 competition

- held in 2020 on Kaggle
- dominated by LightGBM: Makridakis et al. (2020), DeepAR and NBEATS also successful
- A team of my students won a Kaggle Gold, 17th in the competition out of $>5.5k$ participants.
- They used an ensemble of LightGBM and pooled (linear) regression.
- The linear regression component from their method alone would have resulted in 19th place

Deep learning for forecasting

Overview: Deep learning for forecasting

- Usually, recent NLP research (LSTM, attention, transformers, ...) is adapted to the time series use case
- Main differences to NLP:
 - most recent observations are the most important ones
 - long-term dependencies are relatively simple and stable (only seasonalities: daily, weekly, yearly)
 - much more noise and uncertainty

Recurrent neural networks

- Overview by Hewamalage et al. (2020)
- Have an internal state which allows them to memorize
- They have problems to learn long memory (Pascanu et al., 2013)
- LSTM mitigates that to a certain extent
- They still work better in practice if used with input and output windows (Hewamalage et al., 2020)
 - making them more “autoregressive”
 - making the state less important
- Recent results suggest that in general RNNs that can be trained and are stable can be well approximated by feed-forward networks (Miller and Hardt, 2018; Miller, 2018)

Convolutional neural networks

- Some results suggest that CNNs work just as well as RNNs for forecasting, but are a lot faster to train (Borovykh et al., 2018)
 - WaveNet (Oord et al., 2016; Sen et al., 2019): causal convolutions, dilations
 - CNNs don't have a state, so windowing needs to cover everything
- Long input windows, especially with dilations
- RNNs are preferable if input windows need to be small, e.g., across series of different length in a global model.

Specialised architectures

- DeepAR (Flunkert et al., 2017): Generative RNN model
- Deep state space models (Rangapuram et al., 2018):
Parametrizes a linear state-space model with an RNN
- Deep Factors for forecasting (Wang et al., 2019):
Combines a local probabilistic model and a global time series that is a linear combination of factors
- NBEATS (Oreshkin et al., 2019): Decomposes series into basis functions, residual stacking
 - State-of-the-art accuracy on M4
 - 2nd place in M5 (as part of an ensemble)

Transformers for forecasting

- Early works: Transformers for forecasting (Li et al., 2019), Temporal Fusion Transformers (TFT) (Lim et al., 2019)
- TFT addresses specifically common time series problems such as how to incorporate static and dynamic past and known future covariates into transformers, obtain prediction intervals etc.
- Reported to work well in practice in many situations
- TFT was already in existence at the time of the M5, but not used by any winning team. Maybe data of M5 was too intermittent?

Transformers for forecasting (2)

- Since 2019: A myriad of variants: Informer, Autoformer, ETSformer, Robformer, FEDformer, ...?
- Usually have plausible ideas of why they should work
- They solve “long sequence time-series forecasting,” which to me seems somewhat an invented problem
- Many of them:
 - Evaluate on the same small amount of datasets, which only represent a small subset of forecasting use cases
 - Use an exchange rate dataset, where they fail to benchmark against naive, and in fact, we have shown that they lose (Hewamalage et al., 2023)
 - Fail to understand that their exchange rate dataset only contains trading days, which means the seasonality shifts around quite arbitrarily, due to the omission of bank holidays
 - Lose against linear models, if those are trained directly for all horizons, as the transformers are (Zeng et al., 2023)

Transformers for forecasting (3)

Zalando has reported a transformer architecture they have in production (Kunz et al., 2023). Works well, but trains on over 350k series.

→ If you have large amounts of data, Transformers should work.

→ If you have small amounts of data, there are strong competitors that will require less computation.

Multivariate forecasting

- Not the same as global models: series need to be aligned, and often have the same length (see also forecastingdata.org)
- Series can influence each other: Cannibalisation and substitution effects, etc.
- The holy grail in retail demand forecasting?
- Difficult and very active research area. Main problems:
 - How to scale methods to thousands of time series?
 - How to have series (products) come and go?
 - How to model changing and complex relationships?
- Usually sparseness constraints: Each series can interact only with few other series

Multivariate forecasting (cont'd)

- Yu et al. (2016): Matrix factorization with temporal regularization
- Lai et al. (2018), LSTNet: CNN feeding into RNN with skip connections
- Sen et al. (2019): Matrix factorization, causal convolutions and attention
- Salinas et al. (2019): Gaussian copulas
- Wu et al. (2020), Sriramulu et al. (2023): Graph neural networks

LLMs for forecasting

LLMs and Foundational models for forecasting

- Pretrained forecasting models (“foundational models”) or using LLMs for forecasting is currently all the fuzz
- TimeGPT, Lag-Llama, Time-LLM, LLMTIME, GPT4TS
- Many of them report performance “better than everyone else”
- I’ve recently pointed out in a post on LinkedIn that they don’t adequately benchmark
- Many of them claim to be the best on M4, when in fact they are worse than the original winner
- Time-LLM benchmarks on M3 quarterly and is worse than most methods from the original competition from 1998, even worse than naive.

LLMs and Foundational models for forecasting (2)

- These models are coming but still not competitive
- Will they work on any possible frequency? Probably yes, at least on the ~20 most common frequencies.
- Will they work with covariates? Maybe with embeddings/some form of dimensionality reduction? Maybe in a way like TabPFN (Hollmann et al., 2022)? Stacking?
- Will they work with your constraints in production on hardware, time frames, privacy/data sharing concerns? Will there be open-source pre-trained models?

→ Still a lot of unknowns.

Special forecasting problems

Special forecasting problems

- External variables
- Intermittent data
- Hierarchical forecasting
- Forecasting in retail
- Interpretability
- Causal Inference
- Predict+Optimize

Conclusions

Conclusions

- Forecasting as a field has come a long way
- Great time to do forecasting as a Machine Learner or Data Scientist
- Machine Learning methods become more and more competitive
- Forecasting is different from text and images: Often lots of noise, lots of uncertainty, no good human benchmarks. Data structure is not too complex.

Conclusions (2)

- New algorithms and techniques are exciting, but they may not be a good fit for every use case
- It is important to understand the use cases and solve the actual problems
- Machine Learning is a field that is very methods-driven...for the good and for the bad
- Try simple things first, as a baseline.

Thank You

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